

Separation of Vanadium and Uranium by Liquid Anion-exchanger

SUPRA BANDYOPADHYAY and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University, Burdwan-713 104

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A rapid and selective method for the extraction of vanadium as $\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)_3^-$ and uranium as $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_3^-$ with liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336 (nitrate form) in chloroform and n-butanol medium respectively have been proposed. The effects of different variables on extraction have been investigated. The nature of the extracted species has been discussed. On the basis of the extraction data, mutual separation of vanadium and uranium also separations from other commonly associated elements have been carried out.

HIGH molecular weight amines have been used extensively for the extraction of various metal ions as anionic complexes¹. It may be used as a promising technique in industries and atomic energy programmes². Not much work has been reported on the extraction of either vanadium³⁻⁵ or uranium^{6,7} alone or on the separation of the two⁸ using liquid anion exchangers. The present communication reports the extraction behaviour of vanadium as $\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)_3^-$ and uranium as $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_3^-$ with Aliquat 336 liquid anion-exchanger in nitrate form, $\text{R}_4\text{N}^+\text{NO}_3^-$ in suitable solvent. The effects of variables, such as pH of the aqueous phase, organic solvent, concentration of the extraction, equilibration time and various foreign ions, etc. have been investigated. On the basis of the extraction data, the mutual separation of vanadium and uranium has been made efficiently.

Experimental

Aliquat 336 (Fluka, A.G.) was practical grade material. The nitrate form of the liquid-exchanger was obtained by treatment with 2 M HNO_3 . Standard solutions of vanadium and uranium were prepared by dissolving NH_4VO_3 (E. Merck, G. R.) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR). All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Absorbance was recorded on a Shimadzu 190 double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer. The pH values were measured with a Systronics 331 expanded pH meter.

General extraction procedure for vanadium: The general extraction procedure is based upon solvent extraction technique. The aqueous phase was made up from a solution (5 ml) containing 300 μg of vanadium. A 5% potassium tartarate solution (1 ml) was then added, pH of the resulting solution adjusted to 5.0 and finally phthalate buffer (2 ml) was added. The aqueous phase was made up to 10

ml and equilibrated in a separatory funnel with 5% v/v liquid-exchanger solution (10 ml) in chloroform for 5 min. The two layers were allowed to settle for about 10 min. The organic phase was then separated carefully to another separatory funnel. To remove the organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with chloroform (5 ml). The resulting chloroform extract was mixed with the earlier separated organic phase. The amount of vanadium present in the aqueous phase was estimated by spectrophotometric method⁹. The pH of the aqueous medium was adjusted to 4.0, then extracted with 0.1% oxine solution (2×5 ml) in chloroform. The absorbance of the extracted solution was measured at 550 nm against a reagent blank. Finally, the concentration of vanadium was determined from a calibration curve. Then, 10 ml of 0.01 M KOH solution was added to the organic phase in the separatory funnel and the mixture was shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to settle. The aqueous phase was carefully withdrawn and again washed with chloroform (5 ml) to remove any entrained solvent present in the separated aqueous phase. The amount of vanadium extracted in that phase was estimated as in the case of aqueous phase.

General extraction procedure for uranium: 250 μg of uranium in a 30% potassium nitrate solution (5 ml) was taken, pH was adjusted to 8.5 and tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane buffer (2 ml) was added. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml was taken in a separatory funnel and was shaken with 5% liquid-exchanger solution (10 ml) in n-butanol for 5 mins. The two layers were allowed to settle for about 10 min. Two phases were then separated carefully as in the case of vanadium separation and the uranium content was estimated in the two phases by spectrophotometric method¹⁰. In this method pH of the aqueous medium was adjusted to 8.8, then extracted

with 1.0% oxine solution (2 × 10 ml) in chloroform. The absorbance of the extracted solution was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank. Finally, the concentration of uranium was determined from a calibration curve.

Separation procedure for vanadium and uranium : To the aqueous solution containing 300 µg of vanadium and 250 µg of uranium after adding 30% nitrate solution (5 ml), pH was adjusted to 8.5 and tris-buffer (2 ml) was added. It was then equilibrated with 5% liquid-exchanger (10 ml) in n-butanol. The two layers were allowed to settle and were separated carefully. As described in general extraction procedure, to remove the organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with chloroform (5 ml). Finally, the uranium content of the organic phase was taken in 2 M nitric acid (10 ml) and then estimated by spectrophotometric method¹⁰.

To the aqueous phase remaining after the separation of uranium, 5% tartarate solution (5 ml) was added, pH adjusted to 5.0 and phthalate-buffer (2 ml) was added. It was equilibrated with 5% liquid-exchanger (10 ml) in chloroform. Two layers were allowed to settle and separated as usual. Finally, as described in general extraction procedure, the vanadium content of the organic phase was taken in 0.01 M KOH solution (10 ml) and then estimated by spectrophotometric method⁹.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH : The extraction behaviour of the two metals with liquid-exchanger at different pH is given in Fig 1. The working pH ranges for quantitative extraction of vanadium and uranium are respectively 4-5.9 and 8-9.6.

Fig 1. Dependence of pH (O) for vanadium and (□) for uranium

Effect of solvents : The extraction behaviour of each of the metal was studied from aqueous solution having a definite pH into various organic solvents containing liquid-exchanger. The results indicate that most quantitative extraction of vanadium occurs with chloroform, the percentage

of extraction being 98.75. Extraction with other solvents shows 78.75% in toluene, 70.0% in n-butanol and 46.25% in 1,2-dichloroethane. With nitrobenzene and isobutyl methyl ketone, emulsion formation was noted. Similarly, for uranium, n-butanol is most effective with percentage of extraction being 98.49. The results with other solvents are as follows : chloroform, 94.02% ; benzene, 93.80% ; toluene, 92.90% ; 1,2-dichloroethane, 88.95% ; and isobutyl methyl ketone, 84.44% . With nitrobenzene an emulsion was formed.

Liquid-exchanger concentration : The effect of extractant concentration was studied by varying the concentration of liquid-exchanger from 0.2% to 10% using the diluents, chloroform for vanadium and n-butanol for uranium. It was found that the extraction increased with increasing extractant concentration and was complete at 5% liquid-exchanger.

Equilibration times : The contact time was varied from 30 s to 10 min. The extraction time was quantitative within 1 min and back-extraction was complete within 2 min. Contact and stripping time was kept 5 min all experiments.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of diverse ions on the quantitative extraction of vanadium and uranium were studied separately by the general extraction procedure. For 30 ppm vanadium and 25 ppm uranium, tolerance limits (within an error of ± 2%) for various ions are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Diverse ions	Tolerance limits (in ppm)	
	For vanadium	For uranium
Ca ⁺⁺	400	350
Str ⁺⁺	400	350
Ba ⁺⁺	400	350
Mg ⁺⁺	500	400
Mn ⁺⁺	200	160
Ni ⁺⁺	200	80
Co ⁺⁺	200	80
Al ⁺⁺⁺	250	120
Cr ⁺⁺⁺	250	100
Fe ^{+++a}	100	100
Cu ^{++b}	200	200
Zn ^{++a}	250	200
Ti ^{IVc}	350	300
Tungstate	150	150
Molybdate	100	80
Sulphate	200	100
Thiosulphate	300	260
Phosphate	400	320
Bromide	400	300
Iodide	400	300

In presence of : ^aphosphate, ^bthiosulphate, ^cfluoride.

Separation of vanadium and uranium : On the basis of the extraction data it has been possible to achieve the typical separation of the two metals in different synthetic mixtures following the procedure given under heading 'Separation procedure for vanadium and uranium'. The results are presented

in Table 2. The method may very well be suggested for the recovery of UO_2^{2+} from various uranium containing ores, like carnotite and uranite, and for the recovery of VO_2^+ from the waste from uranium extractions.

Sample No.	Composition (Amounts in μg)	Metals extracted, %	
		Vanadium	Uranium
1	$V^{5+}(300) + U^{4+}(250)$	99.5	100.0
2	$V^{5+}(300) + U^{4+}(250) + Ca^{2+}(100) + Mg^{2+}(100) + Ba^{2+}(100)$	102.0	98.4
3	$V^{5+}(300) + U^{4+}(250) + Al^{3+}(50) + Cr^{3+}(40) + Co^{2+}(40)$	98.8	101.0
4	$V^{5+}(300) + U^{4+}(250) + SO_4^{2-}(50) + PO_4^{3-}(50) + Br^-(50)$	98.5	99.5

Nature of the extracted species: The molar concentration of the liquid anion-exchanger was determined by stripping the chloride by sodium hydroxide solution and then titrating the chloride with standard $AgNO_3$ solution using K_2CrO_4 as an indicator.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log D$ against $\log [\text{Aliquat 336}]$: (O) for vanadium and (□) for uranium.

In strong acid solutions, vanadate forms VO_2^+ . V^{5+} forms negatively charged complexes with tartaric acid and potassium tartarate (concentration range 2-10%)¹¹. On this basis, the separation may be accomplished by the liquid anion-exchanger. At a definite concentration of vanadium, the extraction of its tartarate complex as a function of liquid anion-exchanger concentration in chloroform was carried out. The extraction of VO_2^+ is quantitative provided the Aliquat 336-vanadium mole ratio is ≥ 3 . Plot (Fig. 2) of $\log D$ against $\log [\text{Aliquat 336}]$ provides a straight line with slope around 3. Thus the extraction mechanism of VO_2^+ may be given as,

where, o is organic phase and a is aqueous phase.

The nitrate form of the liquid-exchanger obtained by treatment of Aliquat 336 with 2 M HNO_3 was taken in n-butanol and treated with the solution of UO_2^{2+} in 30% nitrate solution. The extraction is quantitative when Aliquat 336-uranium mole ratio is ≥ 1 . Plot (Fig 2) of $\log D$ against $\log[\text{Aliquat 336}]$ produces a straight line with slope approximately 1. Hence, the extraction mechanism of UO_2^{2+} similar to reported earlier¹² may be given as

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